

Checklist for the responsible preservation of research data

Where to start

- Identify a coherent dataset to preserve.
- Find out how long the data should be kept, taking into account guidelines and regulations.
- Make sure that you have sufficient usage rights to submit the data for preservation.
- Find a preservation service suited to your data. For help visit [re3data](https://re3data.org/).
- Ensure your data contain no sensitive personal information or any other confidential data. Or choose a data archive specifically designed to store sensitive personal information data securely.

Preparation of the dataset

- Whenever possible, prefer persistent, open, and common file formats.
- Create a clear folder structure for the dataset.
- Name files and folders in a consistent and descriptive manner.

Description of data

- Ensure your data are understandable and usable by describing them with thorough metadata.
- Give your dataset a clear and descriptive title.
- Create a separate README.txt file to explain the contents of the data.
- If your dataset includes tables, define and explain all column headings, variable values, abbreviations and any codes used.
- Include supporting documentation that helps others understand and use the data, such as descriptions of research methods, questionnaires, consent form templates or digital notes.
- Add links to related research outputs in the dataset's metadata, such as DOIs for published articles, project website URLs or links to any code or software produced during the study.

Licences

- Choose a licence suited to your dataset. For further information, see the [licence guide of OpenAIRE](#).

What to do after you openly shared, published or preserved the data?

- If the data repository you use assigns a DOI or another permanent identifier to your material, include it in the data availability statement of your published article.
- Remember to cite the research data in your article and include the data citation in the reference list.
- Tell others about the data you share! For example, you can add a mention with links to your CV.
- Remember to destroy extra copies and outdated versions of the data.